

showing significant differences ($t, d.f @ 0.05 = 4.76$) between the two. Total yield loss caused by finches was about 100 kg/ha, which is affordable. However, when

all species of birds including parakeets, are considered, losses were found economically important. ■

Environment

Effect of plant density on methane emission from transplanted rice

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An agronomic practice that helps to increase rice production should be environmentally benign. Increasing the plant population is one of the crop management practices considered for increasing rice productivity. However, because the rice plant acts as a conduit through which CH_4 produced in the soil

is transported to the atmosphere, increasing the plant population could have an adverse effect on the environment if CH_4 emission is increased.

To investigate the effect of plant density on CH_4 emission by transplanted rice, a greenhouse experiment was conducted in 1993. In plastic-lined wooden boxes (1.0 m $\times$ 0.5 m $\times$ 0.3 m), 120 kg of Guthrie soil (Typic Fragiaquults, pH 6.5 after flooding, 2.2% organic matter, 48% silt, 30% clay) was submerged for 1 wk and then puddled. Chopped rice straw (about 3 cm) at the rate of 2 t/ha was incorporated 3 wk before transplanting 4-wk-old IR36 rice seedlings. Fertilizers were applied at rates of 60 kg N/ha as prilled urea, 15 kg P/ha as triple superphosphate, and 80 kg K/ha

as potassium chloride. Plant densities, geometrics, and spacing used are illustrated in Figure 1. Four seedlings were transplanted/hill for all spacings; for the regular 20- $\times$ -20-cm spacing, 10 seedlings/hill were also transplanted.

Methane emissions were measured from 0800 h to 1100 h, using the static Plexiglas chamber technique (Fig. 2c). Each chamber covered 4 hills. Ten-ml plastic syringes fitted with Mininert syringe valves were used to take air samples from the chambers immediately after installation and after 30 min. A gas chromatograph (Hewlett Packard, Model 5830 A, equipped with a flame ionization detector and a Poropak Q column) was used to determine CH_4 concentrations of the air samples collected at 26,

1. Transplanting geometries, spacings, plant densities (hills/m²), and areas covered by Plexiglas chambers used for measuring CH_4 emission from 4 rice hills.

2. Methane emission from transplanted rice (IR36) over time as influenced by plant density. Inset (c) illustrates the static Plexiglas chamber technique used. IFDC, 1993.

33, 40, 47, and 55 d after transplanting (DAT).

As the number of hills/m² increased from 25 to 66 (Fig. 2a) and the seedlings/hill increased from 4 to 10 (Fig. 2b), CH₄ emission increased up to 33 DAT. At 26 DAT, emission increased from 20 to 34 mg CH₄/m² per h as the number of hills/m² increased from 25 to 66. This effect of plant density on CH₄ emission, however, diminished with time and disappeared at 40 DAT. This suggests that other plant factors, such as root development and tiller formation,

influenced the effect. When the root systems of the transplanted seedlings are small and limited, the additional hills/m² and/or tillers/m² may effectively serve as additional conduits for transporting more CH₄ from the soil to the atmosphere during the first 33 DAT. Thereafter, the roots of the rice plants develop and spread through a larger soil volume, thereby reaching more CH₄ produced farther away from the plants. During the same period, the number of tillers/hill will increase with time. At 33 DAT, there were 48 and 41 tillers/4 hills for

plant densities of 25 and 66 hills/m², respectively.

The CH₄ emissions from plants with the regular and modified 20- × 20-cm spacing and 4 seedlings/hill were the same (data not reported), probably because both spacings have the same plant density of 25 hills/m² (Fig. 1).

These results suggest that plant density is an important factor and therefore should be defined in field measurements of CH₄ emission from flooded rice, especially during the first month after transplanting. ■

Socioeconomic impact

Labor allocation in rice cultivation in Western Himalaya, Himachal Pradesh, India

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Rice cultivation is a labor-intensive activity that provides employment, particularly to poor and landless female

workers. Despite their active participation in this work, few studies have quantified their labor contributions—particularly for unpaid family labor. Thus, their participation had been underestimated in agricultural statistics. This study was conducted to examine the labor contributions of female and male workers (family and hired) in rice cultivation for different categories of farm and crop operations, to identify constraints to increasing rice productivity with special emphasis on

farm women, and to recommend interventions to improve their status.

We hypothesized that female participation decreases as farm size increases. We surveyed 120 households in 10 villages in two blocks of Kangara District of Himachal Pradesh. Farms were classified as marginal (<1 ha) (60), small (1-2 ha) (33), and large (>2 ha) (27).

Rice farming is the major source of livelihood in this district. Farmers also grow wheat, maize, millet, and sugarcane.

Share of female labor to total labor input (%) in rice cultivation by activity and farm size. Kangara District, Himachal Pradesh, India.

Activity	Farm size							
	Marginal		Small		Large		All farms	
	Total labor input	Female labor to total labor input	Total labor input	Female labor to total labor input	Total labor input	Female labor to total labor input	Total labor input	Female labor to total labor input
Land preparation	13.2 (17.16) ^a	45.0 (7.72)	11.7 (17.67)	41.4 (7.32)	11.4 (12.31)	38.7 (4.76)	12.1 (15.83)	41.6 (6.58)
Planting	25.0 (32.50)	57.2 (18.59)	24.9 (37.60)	60.8 (22.86)	24.6 (26.57)	57.6 (15.30)	24.7 (32.31)	58.6 (18.93)
Interculture	17.6 (22.88)	63.2 (14.46)	21.8 (32.92)	55.2 (18.17)	20.9 (22.57)	53.3 (12.03)	20.2 (26.42)	57.3 (15.14)
Harvesting	32.8 (42.64)	51.8 (22.09)	30.5 (46.05)	55.6 (25.60)	30.6 (33.05)	48.2 (15.93)	31.3 (40.95)	51.8 (21.21)
Postharvest	10.3 (13.39)	74.0 (9.91)	8.9 (13.44)	81.7 (10.98)	9.4 (10.15)	71.6 (7.27)	9.6 (12.56)	75.8 (9.49)
Others	1.1 (1.43)	40.0 (0.57)	2.2 (3.32)	-	3.1 (3.35)	-	2.1 (2.75)	13.3 (0.36)
Total	100.0 (130)	52.6 (68.38)	100.0 (151)	54.8 (82.75)	100.0 (108)	51.2 (55.30)	100.0 (130.82)	52.9 (69.20)

^aFigures in parentheses indicate labor days/ha.